

Supplementary material

Stimulation-mediated reverse engineering of silent neural networks

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Supplementary figures:

Supplementary figure 1. Stimulation-dependent precision of derived weights. Left: average RMSE of derived weights decreased rapidly within less than 100 iterations. Right: larger number of stimuli resulted in more accurate derived weights.

Supplementary figure 2. Prediction of presynaptic weights for fractions network available for supervised learning. (a) Predicted synaptic weights vs actual synaptic weights of silent non-stimulated (left column) and stimulated (right column) network for different fractions (25%, 50%, 75%, 100% from top to bottom) of the network fed to the perceptron. Predicted weights are more accurate for the stimulated network, for all fractions (Pearson correlation, $r > 0.86$, $p \sim 0$) **(b)** RMSE of different fractions of the network. RMSE is decreased for stimulated networks.

Supplementary figure 3. Spike prediction using the derived connection weights for fully active network condition (a) Three examples of spike trains of the postsynaptic neuron in the ground-truth test data (top), predicted spikes using derived weights in the non-stimulated population (middle), and stimulated population (bottom). Blue spikes are true positives. Light grey spikes are false positives. Dark grey spikes are false negatives (b) Sensitivity of spike prediction as a function of stimulus number. The shaded area around the curve shows the standard deviation ($n = 10$). (c) Precision of spike prediction as a function of stimulus number.

Supplementary figure 4. Deriving synaptic weights using indiscriminate synchronized stimulation. (a) Spike raster of the population spike trains. The top 34% of the trains correspond to active neurons and the bottom 66% correspond to silent neurons (see Methods). Stimulation was applied synchronously and is shown by the red bar. (b). Derived weights from a population stimulated synchronously did not match the actual weights ($r = 0.34$, $p = \sim 0$).